

VARICELLA IN BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract.

Varicella is one of the most common diseases in childhood. The disease is caused by a virus belonging to the α -type of herpesvirus with a short reproduction cycle and a cytopathic effect in cells. With a latent infection, the virus is localized in the nerve ganglia and neurons. Varicella is characterized by frequent complications, lifelong persistence of the virus and the possibility of death. In recent years, throughout Uzbekistan, there has been a high incidence of varicella among children. So, in the Bukhara region, the incidence of chickenpox, according to annual statistics for 2020, is 47 children of the corresponding age. Annually from 5 to 6% of cases are adults. The number of sick adolescents aged 15 to 17 years is 2-3%.

Key words: Varicella, children, virus, death, disease

Immune mechanisms largely determine the pathogenesis of congenital infections. Thus, the ability of fetal T-lymphocytes to recognize one's own and another's and cytotoxicity appear from the 16th-17th week of gestation. B-lymphocytes carrying surface immunoglobulins IgM and G are detected at the 9-12th week, their number increases sharply by the 15-16th week of gestation. The production of immunoglobulins by the fetus is low, and by the time of birth, the level of IgM in his blood is 10-15%, IgG - 70-80% of the norm in an adult, and IgA is found in trace amounts. With intrauterine infection, the synthesis of immunoglobulins by the fetus is activated primarily due to IgM, but the assembly of IgM monomers into pentamers is impaired. Congenital chickenpox develops when a pregnant woman develops a rash between 5 and 2 days before delivery due to the lack of transplacental transmission of maternal antibodies. In a newborn, the disease develops from the 6th to the 11th day of life. Chickenpox occurs in severe or moderate forms. Extensive bronchopneumonia often develops, it is possible to develop generalized forms with damage to internal organs. If infection occurred less than 10 days before delivery, neonatal chickenpox occurs with encephalitis. The tropism of the antigen of the varicella zoster virus to the epithelium of the lower respiratory tract was revealed by the immunohistochemical method. Virus expression was noted in epithelial cells of segmental bronchi. The presence of horny scales and meconium bodies in the lumen of the alveoli indicates aspiration of amniotic

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fluid. Leukocyte infiltration in the lumen of the alveoli and destruction of the walls of the alveoli in the presence of inflammatory changes in the walls of small bronchi indicate the development of focal bacterial bronchopneumonia.

